

Title: Systematic approaches to understanding cyberbullying from different angles: contexts, consequences, and moderators

Integrative statement:

This symposium presents and discusses four systematic review studies that analyze contexts, impacts, and moderating factors in cyberbullying to advance a global understanding. They offer insights into the current state of cyberbullying research and outline different approaches to understanding cyberbullying among youths. These studies are conducted under the PARTICIPATE Marie Curie Research project, aiming to create new research evidence for effectively preventing cyberbullying involving various stakeholders such as youths, families, schools, and industry.

The first scoping review explores the tension between parental digital mediation strategies and children's digital rights regarding children's online experiences and identifies factors influencing these strategies. The second scoping review takes a culturally sensitive approach by analyzing empirical studies that explore the cyberbullying experiences of ethnic minorities and Indigenous youth to broaden the understanding of cyberbullying within diverse cultural contexts. The third study aims to understand the connection between children's involvement in bullying and their exposure to violence or bullying by adults within their immediate environments, such as family members or authority figures. The final study is a meta-analysis investigating atypical family and school-related factors that may moderate the association between cyberbullying victimization and internalizing problems.

While the scoping review studies will help to identify research gaps in existing research and provide a background for further empirical studies, the meta-analysis is expected to provide broadly applicable results, contributing to evidence-based strategies for minimizing the psychological impact of cyberbullying on youths. The findings offer a comprehensive perspective on cyberbullying, aiming to inform future research and intervention efforts.

Keywords: Systematic reviews, cyberbullying, prevention, intervention

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Individual abstracts:

Exploring Children's Rights in the Digital Age with the Context of Parental Mediation Styles: A Scoping Review

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The digital age has transformed childhood experiences, with children increasingly engaging with smartphones, social media, and online platforms. The focus of this scoping review is to understand the tension between parental digital mediation style and children's rights in the digital space. It also aims to clarify the relationship between mediation approaches and factors influencing these strategies, including parents' digital skills, communication styles, and children's age and gender. The review is guided by Arksey and O'Malley's (2005) five-stage framework, alongside PRISMA guidelines. This review analyzes 52 studies sourced from ERIC, Scopus, Web of Science, and PsycINFO. Results reveal that age appears to be a significant factor, with younger children experiencing more restrictive strategies, whereas older children are allowed more autonomy. Findings on gender roles were less consistent throughout the articles. Parents with higher digital literacy are more likely to adopt active, enabling mediation approaches. The review underscores the importance of open communication, suggesting that parent-child interaction promotes active mediation over restrictive control. Notably, only four of the reviewed articles directly addressed children's rights in the context of parental mediation, highlighting a research gap. Future research should prioritize direct engagement with children, rather than privileging adult perspectives, to better understand their needs and rights in the digital space. This approach will contribute to more inclusive and effective strategies for managing children's online experiences.

Keywords: Children's digital rights, parental mediation, digital technology, online experience

Cyberbullying related to ethnicity or Indigeneity among children and adolescents: a systematic scoping review

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Ethnic minorities and Indigenous people may represent particularly vulnerable populations for cyberbullying involvement. The scarce existing literature is characterized by conceptual confusion and methodological heterogeneity, leading to the need for a scoping review to map research in this area. The aim of the present work is to provide an overview of empirical research worldwide on cyberbullying related to ethnicity or Indigeneity among young people, by summarizing aspects of conceptualization, methodology, and results.

The scoping review has been carried out in accordance with JBI guidelines and results have been reported following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews. The following databases were searched for study selection: Academic Search Premier, ERIC, PsychINFO (OVID), PubMed, Scopus, SocINDEX, Web of Science, Medline, Proquest. The review includes peer-reviewed studies considering at least children and adolescents aged between 6 and 18 years old belonging to an ethnic minority or Indigenous group, reporting data on cyberbullying related to ethnicity or Indigeneity, and published in English.

From the database search, 6239 articles have been retrieved and, after duplicates removal (n = 3072), 3167 articles remained and screened for title and abstract. Preliminary insights from the screening

have shown scarcity of literature involving Indigenous populations, while people with migrant backgrounds have been more represented in scientific research.

The findings from the present scoping review will inform researchers about aspects of cyberbullying related to ethnicity or Indigeneity that need further investigation and can provide relevant insights for policymakers.

Keywords: ethnic-racial identity; Indigenous; migrants; online bullying; youths.

The connection between children becoming peer bullying perpetrators and experiencing or witnessing violence/bullying by adults: a scoping review

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This scoping review examines the link between children becoming bullying perpetrators and their experiences of violence or bullying by adults through 88 studies. The review aims to map existing evidence of how exposure to adult violence—direct or witnessed—relates to children engaging in peer bullying. The methodology follows JBI guidelines and utilizes Academic Search, Eric, Socindex, Psychinfo, Web of Science and Scopus databases. Studies from diverse global contexts, the majority of them coming from the U.S. and China, reveal that children exposed to parental maltreatment, harsh discipline, or community violence show higher tendencies for bullying, including cyberbullying. The findings indicate a significant connection between parental or family maltreatment and children's bullying behaviors, as suggested by the social cognition theory. However, a research gap exists regarding the influence of adult authority figures, such as teachers.

Moreover, it was found that the studies rarely addressed socioeconomic influences, though findings suggest that financial hardship correlates with both exposure to violence and bullying perpetration. The review highlights the need for further research, especially longitudinal studies, to explore how adult behaviors shape children's bullying roles across varied environments. This study emphasizes the importance of considering adult behavior as a critical factor in peer bullying interventions.

Keywords: Family abuse, teacher bullying, community violence, domestic violence, social cognition theory, bullying motivation

Meta-regression analysis to investigate atypical moderators: The role of school and family factors in moderating cyberbullying victimization outcomes

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Although family and school factors may moderate the associations of offline and cyberbullying with internalizing problems, this hypothesis has never been investigated in a meta-analysis. Therefore, this meta-analysis is conducted to investigate the roles of family and school factors in developing internalizing problems in young people following offline and cyberbullying victimizations.

This meta-analysis is conducted as an extension of Barlett et al. (2024), and the same databases are screened starting from their deadline, January 2022. For the previous literature, studies examined

cyberbullying victimization outcomes in Barlett et al. (2024) are included. The search strings and inclusion and exclusion criteria are revised to align with the objectives of the current study. Studies investigating the role of family and school-related risk and protective factors in internalizing problems of children and adolescents following cyberbullying and offline bullying incidences are included. Rigorous screening and data extraction processes are conducted with two independent reviewers, and Cohen's Kappa values are computed.

In the result of the database search, including articles from Barlett et al. (2024), 3425 articles and after the removal of the duplicates, 2164 articles remain for the title and abstract screening. Following this, 434 articles are retrieved for the full-text screening.

The main effect size of cyberbullying victimization on internalizing problems of young people, controlling for offline bullying and the interaction of family and school-related factors, atypical moderators of meta-analysis, is investigated. We expect the findings will provide a comprehensive perspective on cyberbullying research and a new, underused statistical analysis for the meta-analysis studies.

Keywords: cyberbullying, victimization, school factors, family factors, internalizing problems.

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